

Comparative review of chemical composition and toxicological evaluation of heated tobacco products compared to regular combustible cigarettes

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Received 9 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 21 October 2025 ♦ Published 28 November 2025

Citation: Momekov G, Kondeva-Burdina M, Slavchev S (2025) Comparative review of chemical composition and toxicological evaluation of heated tobacco products compared to regular combustible cigarettes. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e174427>

Abstract

Heated tobacco products (HTPs) are a new category of tobacco products that deliver nicotine by heating tobacco at temperatures of 300–350 °C, thereby avoiding the combustion process typical of conventional cigarettes (CCs). A comprehensive comparative review of the scientific literature was conducted, including independent studies and regulatory assessments by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European agencies (BfR, RIVM), as well as data from international laboratories that are members of the WHO TobLabNet network. In addition, data from peer-reviewed studies conducted by the THS manufacturer—approved for publication and available in the ClinicalTrials.gov database—were examined. Emission data for harmful and potentially harmful constituents (HPHCs) were analyzed under standardized testing conditions. HTPs demonstrate a significantly reduced chemical and toxicological profile compared to CCs due to the absence of combustion. These findings support the potential of HTPs as an alternative with markedly reduced risk for adult CC smokers who are unable or unwilling to quit tobacco use completely.

Keywords

3R4F, conventional cigarettes, harmful and potentially harmful constituents, heated tobacco products, IQOS, THS, tobacco harm reduction, toxicological assessment

Introduction

Tobacco use is a global health problem affecting more than one billion people worldwide, and smoking (predominantly CC use) has been proven to be the largest cause of morbidity and mortality associated with tobacco use (Abrams et al. 2018a). Epidemiological studies have found significantly increased risks of lung cancer, car-

diovascular disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) among CC smokers (Ramstrom and Wikmans 2014). The high level of toxicity of CC smoke is mainly due to combustion at temperatures from 650 °C to 900 °C (Baker 2006), which generates more than 6,000 chemical compounds, including about 100 identified HPHCs causally associated with smoking-related diseases (Fowles and Dybing 2003; WHO 2008; Rodgman and Per-

fetti 2016). Various constituents of tobacco leaves, such as carbohydrates, biopolymers, waxes, and proteins, degrade at the high temperatures of the self-sustaining smoldering process, releasing toxic compounds into cigarette smoke (Torikai et al. 2004; Torikai et al. 2005).

In response to these health challenges, heated tobacco products (HTPs) have been developed as a new technological solution to tobacco use, reducing toxic exposure while maintaining nicotine delivery. THS heats tobacco at temperatures of 300–350 °C, thereby excluding the combustion process and thus reducing the formation of and exposure to toxic substances, while maintaining a satisfactory amount of nicotine inhaled by users in the form of aerosol (Forster et al. 2015), not smoke. Regulators have abandoned strategies aimed at reducing the toxicity of CCs, having recognized the failure of “light” cigarettes in this regard. Hence, attention has shifted to the potential of non-combustible alternatives such as HTPs and other smokeless nicotine substitutes for CCs, which can provide significantly lower exposure to toxic substances for smokers who are unable or unwilling to quit tobacco completely (EU 2014; Abrams et al. 2018b).

The WHO Tobacco Regulation Study Group has identified 39 priority toxic substances to be monitored, recommending 9 of them as key compounds for mandatory reduction: acetaldehyde, acrolein, benzene, benzopyrene, 1,3-butadiene, carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, NNK, and NNN (Burns et al. 2008; WHO 2008, 2019; Piade et al. 2013). In parallel, the FDA has compiled a list of 93 HPHCs, requiring reporting for 18 of them in cigarette smoke (FDA 2012a). Although independent regulatory agencies and scientific institutes, including the German BfR (Mallok et al. 2019), the Dutch RIVM (Dutch RIVM 2018), and laboratories from the WHO TobLabNet network (Bekki et al. 2017; Li et al. 2019), have carried out their own assessments of HTPs, a comprehensive systematic analysis of the scientific evidence on comparative toxicity between HTPs and CCs has not yet been made available.

This study addresses this gap through a comprehensive comparative review of the scientific literature, including independent peer-reviewed studies, regulatory documents from the FDA (US FDA 2016, 2020, 2021), European government agencies (Dutch RIVM 2018; Mallok et al. 2019; Superior Health Council Belgium 2020), data from accredited international laboratories (WHO 2021), and HTP manufacturer’s studies validated by independent research groups. The analysis focused on HPHC emissions and toxicological profiles under standardized testing conditions (ISO and Health Canada Intense regimes) (Health Canada 2000), comparing the most widely studied tobacco heating system, THS/IQOS, with the reference conventional cigarette 3R4F (Smith and Hansch 2000). The review results revealed that HTPs demonstrated an 85–95% reduction in most HPHCs (Jaccard et al. 2017; Farsalinos et al. 2018; Poget et al. 2021), including key carcinogens and the nine toxic substances in cigarette smoke recommended by the WHO for mandatory reduction (Hecht 1999), while maintaining comparable nicotine levels. This analysis provides a necessary scientific basis for understanding the comparative risk between HTPs

and CCs, with potential applications in regulatory policy through tobacco harm reduction strategies, in addition to smoking abstinence strategies (Abrams et al. 2018a, 2018b).

Materials and methods

Literature search strategy

A comprehensive comparative review of the scientific literature for the period 1997–2024 was conducted (Witschi et al. 1997; Smith and Hansch 2000; Valavanidis et al. 2009; Rodgman and Perfetti 2016) by searching the following databases: PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and regulatory archives. The English keywords used were “heated tobacco products,” “IQOS,” “THS,” “HPHC,” “harmful and potentially harmful constituents,” “3R4F,” “cigarette emissions,” and “toxicological assessment.”

Additionally, publications from the list of PMI (Philip Morris International) studies, comprising 20 peer-reviewed scientific articles (2015–2024), as well as fundamental studies on the characterization of harmful constituents in cigarette smoke from the late 1990s, were analyzed (Witschi et al. 1997; Smith and Hansch 2000).

Inclusion criteria

The comprehensive comparative review includes:

- Peer-reviewed scientific publications comparing emissions and/or toxicological profiles of HTPs and conventional cigarettes (CCs).
- Fundamental research on toxic constituents in cigarette smoke (1997–2000) (Witschi et al. 1997; Kunze et al. 1998; Hecht 1999; Smith and Hansch 2000).
- Official regulatory documents and assessments by the FDA (FDA 2012a, 2012b; US FDA 2016, 2020, 2021), European health agencies (BfR, RIVM) (Dutch RIVM 2018; Mallok et al. 2019), and other national health authorities (Committee on Toxicity 2017; Public Health England 2018) (15 documents from 2017–2022).
- Studies by accredited laboratories that are members of the WHO TobLabNet network (Bekki et al. 2017; Li et al. 2019).
- Independent academic research (41 third-party publications, 2017–2024) (Stephens 2017; Farsalinos et al. 2018; Karkela et al. 2022).
- Papers analyzing emissions of harmful and potentially harmful constituents (HPHCs) under standardized testing conditions (ISO and Health Canada Intense regimes) (Health Canada 1999).
- Toxicological studies (*in vitro*, *in vivo*) and cohort studies for biomarkers of exposure (Gonzalez-Suarez et al. 2015; Wong et al. 2016; Polosa et al. 2021).
- WHO regulatory frameworks for the assessment of tobacco products, including the WHO Technical Report Series from 2008 to 2023 (WHO 2005, 2008).

Exclusion criteria

Excluded were:

- Research focused exclusively on e-cigarettes without comparison to HTPs or CCs.
- Studies on other smokeless tobacco products (snus, chewing tobacco) without relevance to products delivering nicotine by inhalation.
- Unpublished or incomplete papers without independent peer review.
- Studies lacking clear methodology or standardized testing conditions, or without comparative data between HTPs and CCs.
- Abstracts or conference presentations containing partial or incomplete information.

Regulatory documents analyzed

Special attention was given to:

- FDA Modified Risk Tobacco Product (MRTP) and Premarket Tobacco Product Application (PMTA) assessments of THS/IQOS with HTPs (2019–2022).
- WHO TobReg guidance on toxic constituents prioritized for monitoring and reduction.
- National health agencies: German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Japanese National Institute of Public Health, and the Committee on Toxicity (COT) of the UK.
- European regulatory standards for tobacco products (TPD 2014/40/EU).
- Report by Public Health England/Office for Health Improvement and Disparities (PHE/OHID).

Data analytics methodology

The analysis is structured into three main areas:

1. **Chemical composition of emissions**—comparison of HPHC concentrations between HTP aerosols and CC smoke under standardized testing conditions, including the characterization of major classes of toxic compounds (aromatic amines, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, and tobacco-specific nitrosamines) based on classic cigarette smoke studies from the late 1990s to the present.
2. **Toxicological assessment**—analysis of independent regulatory assessments, in vitro toxicological

tests (Ames, micronuclei, cytotoxicity), in vivo studies, and systemic toxicology (Schaller et al. 2016a, 2016b).

3. **Cohort and clinical studies**—evaluation of biomarkers of exposure, short-term clinical studies, and long-term follow-up.

Focus of the study

The main focus is on the tobacco heating system THS/IQOS due to its extensive scientific documentation (a total of 76 publications analyzed) and regulatory assessment compared to the reference 3R4F cigarette, which serves as the standard for CCs in laboratory studies (Smith and Hansch 2000). Both scientifically validated data from industry and independent studies were analyzed to provide a comprehensive and balanced assessment of the available scientific evidence.

Results

1. Chemical composition and emissions

Analysis of the chemical composition of HTP emissions compared to CCs reveals significant quantitative differences in the content of the main aerosol components (Peitsch and Hoeng 2021).

As shown in Table 1, standardized measurements according to ISO protocols demonstrate the characteristic features of aerosols from both types of tobacco products.

Main aerosol components

A comparative analysis of the main aerosol components between the reference 3R4F cigarette and HTP with THS shows the following key differences (Schaller et al. 2016a):

- **Glycerol**—HTPs demonstrated an increased content (5.02 ± 0.101 mg/unit) compared to 3R4F (2.08 ± 0.113 mg/unit), reflecting the specific composition of the tobacco substrate in HTPs. Glycerol is present in HTPs as an aerosol-forming chemical and is not classified as a toxicant (HPHC).
- **Nicotine**—HTPs provide comparable amounts of nicotine to CCs (1.29 ± 0.047 mg/unit for HTP versus 1.74 ± 0.039 mg/unit for 3R4F), ensuring satisfactory nicotine delivery to users.
- **Water**—The water content of HTP aerosol (30.2 ± 2.17 mg/unit) is significantly higher than that of 3R4F smoke (14.7 ± 2.10 mg/unit).

Table 1. Main suppliers of aerosols for HTP and CC–3R4F.

Capturing of aerosols defined in accordance with ISO 4387; 8454; 10315	Unit	CC (3R4F)			HTPS (THS/IQOS)		
		Average	SD	n	Average	SD	n
Glycerin	mg/product	2.08	0.113	2	5.02	0.101	3
Nicotine	mg/product	1.74	0.039	2	1.29	0.047	3
Water	mg/product	14.7	2.10	2	30.2	2.17	3

Reduction of harmful and potentially harmful constituents (HPHCs)

The most significant conclusion of the chemical analyses is the consistent and substantial reduction of HPHCs in aerosols from HTPs compared to CCs. PMI studies demonstrated an average decrease of about 85–95% in 58 HPHC substances (including those from the WHO list of nine and the FDA list of 18 HPHCs) in HTP aerosol (version THS 2.2) compared to HPHC levels in CCs. This decrease in HPHCs has been confirmed by several independent studies (Jaccard et al. 2017; Davigo et al. 2023; Ghazi et al. 2024).

Specific data on reduction by constituent

The levels of carbonyl compounds were shown to be significantly reduced in HTPs compared to CCs (Farsalinos et al. 2018). Under the Health Canada Intense Testing Regime (Health Canada 1999), HTPs emit markedly lower levels of all major carbonyls:

- Formaldehyde—reduced by approximately 91.6%
- Acetaldehyde—reduced by approximately 84.9%
- Acrolein—reduced by approximately 90.6%
- Propionaldehyde—reduced by approximately 89.0%
- Crotonaldehyde—reduced by approximately 95.3%

Independent studies confirm these findings, also showing that HTPs emit about half the nicotine and significantly lower levels of harmful substances compared to cigarettes (Davigo et al. 2023).

Toxic gases also show a drastic decrease (Schaller et al. 2016a; Bekki et al. 2017):

- Carbon monoxide (CO)—decreased by 99% (one hundredth of the levels in CCs; CO is a marker of combustion, practically negligible).
- Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)—total reduction of 81.2%.
- Carcinogenic compounds show significant decreases (Fig. 1) (Stephens 2017; Bekki et al. 2017; Slob et al. 2020; Karkela et al. 2022; Davigo et al. 2023):
- Benzene, 1,3-butadiene, benzo[a]pyrene—reduced by more than 80%.
- Tobacco-specific nitrosamines (TSNAs)—the concentrations of NNK and NNN are reduced to one-fifth (an 80% decrease).

Numerous independent studies confirm these data (Mallok et al. 2018; Uchiyama et al. 2018; Hidayat and Alayyannur 2021; Lu et al. 2021; Perezhogina et al. 2021; Szparaga et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2021a, b).

The WHO Study Group on Tobacco Regulation (TobReg) has identified priority substances whose concentrations in tobacco product emissions are an important criterion for regulation. Despite thousands of compounds in tobacco product emissions, including hundreds of toxic substances—some of which are carcinogenic—TobReg designates 39 substances for ongoing monitoring and recommends mandatory reductions in the levels of nine of them in cigarette smoke as the most toxic: acetaldehyde, acrolein, benzene,

Figure 1. Comparative emissions of HPHCs from reference cigarettes 3R4F (CCs) and HTPs. The values are presented in µg/unit.

benzo[a]pyrene, 1,3-butadiene, carbon monoxide (CO), formaldehyde, 4-(methyl-nitrosamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK), and N-nitrosornicotine (NNN) (WHO 2008). The most important criterion for selecting toxic compounds to be regulated is evidence of their toxicity, with particular attention to compounds associated with cardiovascular toxicity, pulmonary toxicity, and carcinogenicity. The list of nine toxic substances may apply to all tobacco products for smoking or inhalation, including non-combustible tobacco products (Fig. 2; Table 2) (WHO 2008).

Stability and consistency of the reductions under different conditions

Studies conducted under extreme climatic conditions confirm the consistent reduction of HPHCs. Under varying temperature and humidity conditions (warm and dry climates—30 °C and 35% relative humidity; warm and very humid climates—30 °C and 75% relative humidity), the HPHC levels in the HTP aerosol remain reduced by at least 90% on average compared to the concentrations in the mainstream smoke of a 3R4F cigarette (Poget et al. 2021).

Solid particles and aerosol structure

Due to the combustion of tobacco, cigarette smoke contains high levels of carbon-based solid particles (approximately 0.5 trillion/cigarette). A significant difference between HTPs and CCs is observed in the structure of the generated particles in cigarette smoke and HTP aerosol. Because combustion is absent, the HTP aerosol is composed of gases and liquid droplets but contains no solid particles (Pratte et al.

2017). Studies have shown that no solid particles are detected in HTP aerosol after passing through a thermal thermodeuder at 300 °C, which is consistent with the fact that there is no combustion process in HTPs. In contrast, about 80% of the total particulate matter in 3R4F smoke consists of solid particles and/or low-volatile liquid droplets.

Non-targeted analytical approach

A complex non-targeted analytical comparison was conducted to identify unique or increased compounds in HTP aerosol versus cigarette smoke. By applying a wide range of LC-MS and GC×GC-MS methods, it was found that only a few compounds were significantly more abundant in HTP aerosol than in cigarette smoke, and some were unique to THS. Overall, the results showed that cigarette smoke is far more complex in composition than HTP aerosol (Bentley et al. 2020; Lang et al. 2024). Advanced analytical techniques, including chromatographic–mass spectrometric methods, confirm these findings and provide a detailed characterization of aerosol components (Heide et al. 2021; Sussman et al. 2023). A significant portion of these compounds have been identified as reaction products of glycerol.

2. Toxicological assessment

The toxicological assessment of HTPs includes an extensive research program covering *in vitro* tests, preclinical animal studies, and clinical studies involving humans. The results of these studies have been evaluated by both independent scientific groups and regulatory authorities in different countries.

Figure 2. Reduced emissions for the nine toxic substances (CCs and HTPs).

Table 2. Reductions of the toxicants included in the WHO list of nine toxic substances in the HTP aerosol compared to 3R4F cigarette smoke.

HPHCs (WHO 9)	Unit of measurement	3R4F reference cigarette		THS 2.2*			THS 3.0**		
		Average	SD	Average	SD	Red. (%)	Average	SD	Red. (%)
Carbon monoxide (CO)	[mg/stick]	30.2	2.76	0.447	0.0893	98.5%	0.324	0.0501	98.9%
1,3-Butadiene	[µg/stick]	98.5	9.8	0.233	0.0185	99.8%	0.14	0.0162	99.9%
Formaldehyd	[µg/stick]	85.2	16.7	8.89	1.17	89.6%	9.03	0.448	89.4%
Acetaldehyde	[µg/stick]	1641	258	215	22.5	86.9%	158	5.28	90.4%
Acrolein	[µg/stick]	156	25.4	11.8	2.61	92.4%	7.95	0.393	94.9%
Benzene	[µg/stick]	81.1	8.78	0.533	0.0198	99.3%	0.348	0.0273	99.6%
N-Nitrozonornicotine (NNN)	[ng/stick]	283	27.8	12.3	0.869	95.7%	10.6	0.847	96.3%
4-(methyl-nitrosamine)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK)	[ng/stick]	264	26.4	8.72	0.554	96.7%	8.95	0.708	96.6%
Benzo[a]pyrene	[ng/stick]	15	1.3	0.621	0.0317	95.9%	0.6	0.057	96.0%

The values of the nine toxic substances in cigarettes, THS 2.2, and THS 3.0.

SD – standard deviation; Nam (%) – reduction expressed in percentages.

*THS 2.2 is the initial version of the PMI THS (blade THS), which uses a blade to heat the tobacco through internal resistive heating. It is commercialized as IQOS 3 or IQOS Originals and designed to be used with HTPs (heatsticks) sold under the brand name HEETS.

**THS 3.0 is the new version of the PMI THS (induction THS), commercialized as IQOS ILUMA. It features internal induction heating technology and uses specially designed HTPs sold under the brand name TERA.

Independent studies

In vitro cytotoxicity and genotoxicity

Standard *in vitro* toxicology tests demonstrate consistent differences between HTPs and CCs. When using a set of standard *in vitro* toxicology tests (Ames, Micronucleus, and Neutral Red Uptake tests), HTPs showed no observable responses, while a significant toxic response from a 3R4F cigarette was observed. Specifically, the Ames test showed no observable response for HTP aerosol compared to 3R4F cigarette smoke, and a significant reduction of 90% in cytotoxicity and 95% in genotoxicity was observed in HTP aerosol compared with cigarette smoke (Buratto et al. 2018).

Various studies have confirmed the reduced cytotoxicity of HTP aerosols (Zagoriti et al. 2020; Caruso et al. 2021; Niu et al. 2023; Merritt et al. 2024; Sood et al. 2024). When examining different methods for assessing cytotoxicity (NRU, MTT, Annexin V apoptosis, high-content screening, and real-time cell analysis), all tests showed reduced cellular viability after exposure to 1R6F reference cigarette smoke and little or no reduction for HTPs within 24 hours (Fig. 3) (Gonzalez-Suarez et al. 2015; Schaller et al. 2016a; Esposito et al. 2022).

The study of 55 HPHCs in different HTPs shows that the levels generated by them were significantly reduced compared to those of 3R4F (Schaller et al. 2016b; Poynton et al. 2017).

Epigenetic effects

Studies on epigenetic effects reveal significant differences between HTPs and CCs. Only CC extract (3R4F at 0.5% concentration) significantly reduced cell proliferation of A549 and BEAS-2B cell lines, while 0.5% extracts from commercially available HTPs did not affect cell growth (Hattori et al. 2020).

The TUNEL test showed that apoptosis occurred in the A549 and BEAS-2B cell lines 24 hours after exposure to 3R4F, while HTPs did not produce similar effects. Only the extract of 3R4F reduced histone H2A phosphorylation in both cell lines, indicating an epigenetic disorder not seen in HTPs (Hattori et al. 2020).

Oxidative stress

HTPs demonstrated significantly lower oxidative toxicity compared to CCs (Lyu et al. 2022). The effects of HTPs, when observed, occurred only at very high, non-physiological concentrations, supporting the reduced harm profile under normal use.

Systemic toxicological assessment

When using a systemic toxicology approach, HTP aerosol induced lower levels of cytotoxicity and smaller changes in secreted pro-inflammatory mediators than 3R4F smoke (Wong et al. 2016).

A meta-analysis of systemic toxicology in three types of human organotypic cultures of the aerodigestive tract (buccal, bronchial, and nasal epithelium) showed lower toxicity in all cultures after exposure to HTP aerosol compared to 3R4F smoke at comparable nicotine concentrations (Iskandar et al. 2017).

Long-term animal studies

An 18-month carcinogenicity study in A/J mice conducted in accordance with OECD Guideline 453 showed that chronic exposure to HTP aerosol did not increase the incidence or multiplicity of bronchioloalveolar adenomas or carcinomas compared to the control group, while exposure to cigarette smoke increased these rates (Wong et al. 2020).

In contrast to mice exposed to HTP aerosol, mice exposed to cigarette smoke showed increased heart weight, changes in red blood cell profiles, and serum parameters

Figure 3. *In vitro* toxicological evaluation of HTPs and reference cigarettes 3R4F (CCs). The results show the relative levels of toxic response, where 3R4F is defined as 100 relative units (reference standard).

of liver function. Increased lung inflammation, altered lung function, and emphysematous changes were observed only in mice exposed to cigarette smoke (Phillips et al. 2015; Wong et al. 2020).

3. Regulatory assessments

FDA (USA) – U.S. Food and Drug Administration

On July 7, 2020, the FDA authorized the IQOS version THS 2.2 with three types of consumables (heatsticks) as a Modified Risk Tobacco Product (MRTP), concluding that scientific evidence demonstrated it was “appropriate for promoting public health and is expected to benefit the health of the general population.” The FDA confirmed the product’s potential to reduce harm and risk of disease compared to continued cigarette smoking (US FDA 2016). Specifically, the FDA found a significant reduction in the formation of harmful and potentially harmful substances compared to cigarette smoke and stated that “it is reasonable to expect that subsequent studies will establish a measurable and substantial reduction in morbidity and mortality in individual users.”

Independent laboratory analyses confirmed more than a 90% reduction in most HPHCs and over an 80% reduction in other substances compared to 3R4F (Bekki et al. 2017; Dutch RIVM 2018; Karkela et al. 2021; Maeder and Jeannet 2025). In one study (Maeder and Jeannet 2025), 105 out of 108 evaluated HPHCs showed an average reduction of more than 91.6% in HTPs compared to 3R4F. Similar results were reported in comparisons of gas-phase and particulate matter between HTPs and 3R4F, with significantly lower emissions and only sporadic particulate matter in the aerosol (Karkela et al. 2021).

BfR (Germany) – Federal Institute for Risk Assessment

Germany’s Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) published an assessment of HTPs in 2018, concluding that they contain fewer harmful substances than CCs but still pose a health risk. The BfR emphasized the need for further long-term studies for a complete risk assessment (Mallock et al. 2019).

RIVM (Netherlands) – National Institute for Public Health and the Environment

The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment of the Netherlands (RIVM) confirmed that IQOS THS emits significantly fewer harmful substances than CCs (Dutch RIVM 2018). RIVM developed a method—Change in Cumulative Exposure (CCE)—to estimate the reduction in cancer risk based on toxicant emissions. The CCE was estimated to be 10- to 25-fold lower when using HTPs instead of cigarettes. Such a reduction indicates a substantially smaller decrease in expected lifespan, based on available dose–response data in smokers (Slob et al. 2020).

WHO TobLabNet laboratories

Member laboratories of the WHO TobLabNet network in Japan and China confirmed significant reductions in HPHCs in HTPs compared to CCs (Bekki et al. 2017; Li et al. 2019). The Japanese laboratory found that the concentration of TSNAs was one-fifth and the carbon monoxide level only one-hundredth of those in CCs. The Chinese laboratory confirmed that, in addition to some carbonyls, ammonia, and N-nitrosoanabasine, the levels of several HPHCs in HTPs were at least 80% lower than those of 3R4F (Bekki et al. 2017).

UK Committee on Toxicity (COT)

The British Committee on Toxicity (COT) published a statement on the toxicological assessment of new HTPs, acknowledging the significant reduction in toxicants but highlighting the need for more data on long-term effects (Committee on Toxicity 2017).

Consensus in regulatory assessments

An extensive review of 17 independent and industry-funded studies shows that the results of these studies and regulatory assessments are approaching a general consensus that HTP aerosols expose consumers to significantly lower levels of toxicity than tobacco smoke (Caruso et al. 2021).

Regulatory agencies in different countries reach similar conclusions regarding the harm reduction potential of HTPs, despite their different methodological approaches and assessment criteria. All emphasize the need for ongoing monitoring and long-term research for full risk characterization (Caruso et al. 2021).

4. In vivo carcinogenic studies

The 18-month study in A/J mice, conducted in accordance with OECD Guideline 453, represents the gold standard for assessing carcinogenic potential (Wong et al. 2020). The results demonstrate fundamental differences between HTPs and CCs in terms of tumorigenesis.

Key findings from long-term studies:

- Chronic exposure to HTP aerosol did not increase the incidence or multiplicity of bronchioloalveolar adenomas or carcinomas compared to the control group (Wong et al. 2020).
- Cigarette smoke significantly increased tumor incidence and multiplicity (Wong et al. 2020).
- The gene profile of tumors in mice exposed to HTP aerosol was similar to that of spontaneous tumors and differed distinctly from the profile of tumors induced by cigarette smoke (Xiang et al. 2021).
- A 13-gene signature was developed that reliably distinguishes tumors associated with exposure to cigarette smoke from spontaneous tumors (Xiang et al. 2021).

Carcinogenic risk assessment

Margin of exposure (MOE) analysis shows significant advantages of HTPs in the carcinogenic risk profile (Auer et al. 2018):

- The carcinogenic risk for CCs indicates elevated risk levels when consuming as few as 10 cigarettes per day (Inoue-Choi et al. 2016).
- Incremental lifetime cancer risk (ILCR) analysis confirmed these findings, with CCs exceeding the safe value of 10^{-4} in some cases (Esposito et al. 2022).
- Cancer potency modeling shows that HTPs have at least one order of magnitude lower carcinogenic potential than tobacco smoke (Stephens 2017).

Effects on specific tissues

Studies on specific tissues reveal consistent patterns of reduced toxicity:

- **Bone tissue**—HTPs are significantly less toxic to bone cells than CCs when analyzing mitochondrial and esterase activity ($P < 0.001$). Harmful effects of HTPs on bone cell function are observed only at very high, non-physiological concentrations (Aspera-Werz et al. 2020).
- **Vocal cords**—Short-term *in vitro* exposure of human fibroblasts from vocal cords to HTPs does not result in cytotoxicity and reduces the gene expression of measured inflammatory mediators (Grossmann et al. 2024).
- **Adipose tissue**—Only CC extract significantly disrupts the differentiation of preadipocytes into beige adipocytes, while HTP extracts do not affect this process (Zagoriti et al. 2020).

Consistent reduction of HPHCs in HTPs

Studies conducted under extreme climatic conditions have demonstrated the robustness of THS technology with HTPs in reducing HPHCs (Poget et al. 2021):

- Under hot and dry conditions (30 °C, 35% RH) and hot and very humid conditions (30 °C, 75% RH), reductions in HPHCs remain above 90%.
- Fifty-four HPHCs show consistent reduction regardless of climate conditions.
- The volumetric-corrected approach confirms a sustained reduction for all investigated HPHCs.

General safety profile

The body of evidence from long-term, clinical, and specialized studies has consistently demonstrated significantly reduced harm from HTPs compared to CCs, supporting their harm reduction potential through heating technology.

5. In vitro toxicological assessment

Basic cytotoxic tests

Standard genotoxic tests demonstrate fundamental differences between HTPs and CCs. When using the Ames test (bacterial reverse mutation test), *in vitro* micronucleus test, and mouse lymphoma assay, HTPs showed no observable responses, whereas CCs induced significant toxic reactions.

Multiple cytotoxic screenings using different methods (NRU, MTT, Annexin V apoptosis, high-content screening assays, real-time cell analysis) in human adenocarcinoma lung epithelial cells (H292) show:

- Decreased cellular viability after exposure to the reference cigarette 1R6F (similar to 3R4F).

- Little or no reduction in viability for HTPs within 24 hours.
- Time-resolved analyses reveal the kinetic dependence of the toxicity of chemicals in smoke/aerosol.

Systemic toxicology with organotypic cultures

The most advanced *in vitro* studies use three-dimensional human organotypic cultures of the aerodigestive tract that accurately reproduce the physiological characteristics of human tissues under exposure to smoke or aerosol (Iskandar et al. 2017).

Buccal epithelial cultures

Exposure of human organotypic oral epithelial tissue cultures (*EpiOral*, MatTek Corporation) to an aerosol of 3R4F or HTPs for 28 minutes at comparable nicotine concentrations (0.32–0.51 mg nicotine/L) revealed (Zanetti et al. 2016):

- A greater impact of 3R4F smoke compared to HTP aerosol in terms of cytotoxicity, morphological tissue alterations, and secretion of inflammatory mediators.
- Significantly impaired network patterns in smoke exposure (apoptosis, necroptosis, aging, xenobiotic metabolism, oxidative stress).
- Markedly reduced stress responses after exposure to HTP aerosol, with exposed cultures recovering more fully.

Bronchial epithelial cultures

In a model of human small airways using a systems toxicology approach that combines functional tests with omics technologies (Iskandar et al. 2017):

- Aerosol from HTPs induces lower levels of cytotoxicity and smaller changes in secreted pro-inflammatory mediators compared to 3R4F smoke.
- The effects of HTPs, when observed, are mostly transient and decrease more rapidly after exposure.
- A higher transcriptome-induced biological impact was observed with 3R4F smoke.

Nasal epithelial cultures

Three-dimensional nasal cultures demonstrated consistent patterns of reduced toxicity in HTPs, with causal network enrichment analysis supporting a similar mechanistic impact of cigarette smoke across all three cultures (Iskandar 2016).

Air–liquid interface (ALI) studies

ALI studies using different human cell lines (A549, BEAS-2B, NCI-H292, NHBE, and NHLF) have shown a consistent reduction in cytotoxicity and inflammatory responses when exposed to HTP aerosol compared to conventional cigarette smoke. Cellular functionality remained preserved at physiologically relevant concentrations for HTPs (Caruso et al. 2021).

- A 90–95% reduction in cytotoxicity in HTPs compared to CCs.
- Significantly lower levels of pro-inflammatory mediators after exposure to HTPs.
- Preserved viability and metabolic activity of cells at physiologically relevant doses of HTPs.

6. Specialized tissue models

Epigenetic and apoptotic effects

A comparative study of the cell lines A549 (human lung carcinoma) and BEAS-2B (normal bronchial epithelium) revealed key differences (Choukrallah et al. 2018; Hattori et al. 2020):

- Conventional cigarette smoke (3R4F extract, 0.5%) significantly reduces cell proliferation and induces apoptosis in both cell lines.
- HTPs (0.5% extracts) do not affect cell growth.
- Smoke from 3R4F alone reduces histone H2A phosphorylation, affecting transcriptional regulation.
- When using 3R4F, increased activity was reported in 339 genes, whereas for HTPs, only 103–107 genes showed increased activity.

Effects on the bone cell system

In human mesenchymal stem cells and primary human preosteoblasts, HTPs showed significantly lower toxicity in mitochondrial and esterase activity analyses ($P < 0.001$), while harmful effects occurred only at nonphysiologically high concentrations. At the same time, CC extracts reduced alkaline phosphatase twofold and matrix mineralization fourfold at low doses (Aspera-Werz et al. 2020).

Adipocyte differentiation

In a study on 3T3-L1 preadipocytes differentiating into beige adipocytes, cigarette smoke extract alone induced a dose- and time-dependent decrease in cell viability. Exposure to HTPs did not disrupt the differentiation process, and lipid accumulation and marker expression remained unchanged (Zagoriti et al. 2020).

Oxidative stress and free radicals

The levels of free nicotine in the aerosol from HTPs and in CC smoke are similar (Shein et al. 2019). The emission of reactive oxygen species (ROS) from HTPs is 85% lower than that from CCs (Salman et al. 2018), and the carbonyl compounds in HTP aerosol are 77% lower (Farsalinos et al. 2018).

Free radical analysis

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy shows that the levels of organic radicals in HTP aerosol do not exceed 1% of those found in 3R4F smoke, and the concentration of nitric oxide (NO) reaches about 7% of the levels in conventional cigarette smoke. Persistent radicals are found only in 3R4F (Shein and Jeschke 2019).

Protein damage and carbonylation

In protein model studies, conventional cigarette extracts lead to higher yields of carbonyl derivatives, while HTP extracts show significantly lower superoxide radical activity and lower production of carbonyl compounds (Merritt et al. 2024). The contribution of reactive aldehydes to protein damage is greater in CC smoke than in HTP aerosol (Merritt et al. 2024).

7. Cohort studies and clinical research

Clinical studies and human biomarkers

Clinical studies in humans confirm laboratory findings of reduced exposure to toxicants:

- A 3-year follow-up of COPD patients using HTPs showed improved health outcomes (Polosa et al. 2021).
- Human biomarkers of exposure demonstrated significant reductions when switching from CCs to HTPs (Lüdicke et al. 2016, 2019; Li et al. 2023).
- Clinical data support the harm reduction potential of HTPs (Akram et al. 2024).

The latest WHO recommendations identify a set of key biomarkers whose exposure levels from HTPs should be monitored: urinary nicotine equivalents (TNEs), *N*'-nitrosonornicotine metabolites (NNAL), cyanoethyl mercapturic acid (CEMA), exhaled carbon monoxide (CO), and salivary propylene glycol (WHO 2022). Clinical data demonstrate significant reductions in biomarkers of toxic exposure when switching from CCs to HTPs, including an 80–90% reduction in exhaled CO and a 50–90% reduction in carboxyhemoglobin (COHb) within one week (WHO 2022). It is important to note that dual use (HTPs + CCs) does not lead to significant reductions in biomarkers of exposure, meaning that only complete switching to HTPs results in reduced harm (WHO 2022).

Three-year follow-up in patients with COPD

The most significant clinical study is a prospective cohort study with a 3-year follow-up of patients affected by COPD who transitioned from CCs to HTPs (Fig. 4). The study included patients with confirmed COPD ($n = 44$) followed up at 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 months (Polosa et al. 2021).

Key clinical outcomes:

- Significant improvement in expiratory flow rate and lung function (% of the predicted)—a major indicator of pulmonary capacity.
- Reduction in respiratory symptoms and the frequency of exacerbations.
- Improvement in quality of life as measured by validated questionnaires.
- Sustained improvements throughout the 36-month follow-up period.

Controlled clinical trials

A randomized controlled trial with 112 healthy volunteer smokers demonstrated objective changes in biomarkers of exposure within 5 days after switching to HTPs (Lüdicke et al. 2016).

Short-term changes (5-day exposure):

Nicotine exposure—Nicotine equivalents and plasma cotinine concentrations remain comparable between HTPs and CCs, providing adequate nicotine delivery for consumers.

- **Carboxyhemoglobin (COHb)**—Decreased by 43% in the HTP group (compared to 55% in the abstinence group and no change in CC smokers).
- **Urinary mutagenicity**—Decreased by 89% in the THS group (87% in the abstinence group), reflecting a drastically reduced potential for mutagenic damage.
- **Largest reduction:** Observed for 1,3-butadiene metabolites (>90% in both the HTP and abstinence groups).
- **Least reduction:** Observed for pyrene metabolites (51% in the HTP and 48% in the abstinence groups).

All biomarkers of exposure measured showed statistically significant reductions in HTPs compared to CCs ($P < 0.0001$ for the main biomarkers), with reductions comparable in magnitude to those observed with complete abstinence from smoking for 5 days.

Population studies

Japan was the first country to launch HTPs and has experienced relatively widespread adoption of heated tobacco products since 2014, allowing assessment of their effects on national trends in CC smoking (Cummings et al. 2020).

National trends in Japan (2011–2019) (Cummings et al. 2020):

- Between 2011 and 2015, sales of CCs decreased at a moderate rate (annual rate of change, ARC -3.10% ; $p = 0.11$).
- Since the introduction of HTPs in 2014, the rate of decline in CC sales has accelerated dramatically to an ARC of -16.38% ($p = 0.0004$)—an almost fivefold decline from the previous period.
- As of 2019, total cigarette sales have decreased by 38%, and combined sales (CCs + HTPs) by 19%.

Comparative studies of nicotine pharmacokinetics

Human pharmacokinetic profiles show similar nicotine delivery between HTPs and CCs but with different toxicity profiles (Lüdicke et al. 2019).

Nicotine kinetics:

- Peak serum nicotine concentrations are comparable between HTPs and CCs (Lüdicke et al. 2019).
- Peak times are slightly longer with HTPs, which may improve product satisfaction (Lüdicke et al. 2019).

Figure 4. Clinical outcomes in patients with COPD after switching to HTPs: 3-year prospective follow-up. Improvements in various health indicators with their specific units of measurement are shown.

- Nicotine levels are more persistent in HTPs due to reduced variability in aerosol delivery (Li et al. 2023).

Correlations with biomarkers:

- Nicotine levels correlate directly with consumer satisfaction in all products studied (Lüdicke et al. 2019).
- Toxic biomarkers show an inverse correlation with nicotine levels in HTPs, in contrast to cigarettes (Li et al. 2023).

Discussion

This comparative review demonstrates the fundamental differences between HTPs and CCs through a multistep analysis, beginning with chemical composition and ending with clinical evidence in humans. The principle of heating rather than burning has been confirmed as an effective strategy for reducing harmful emissions while preserving the delivery of nicotine necessary for consumer satisfaction (Kunze et al. 1998; Lüdicke et al. 2019).

Temperature control during heating at approximately 350 °C, compared with more than 600 °C for combustion, is the main factor explaining the 85–95% reduction in most HPHCs (Torikai et al. 2004; Torikai et al. 2005; Baker 2006; Jaccard et al. 2017). This confirms the scientific validity of the technological approach and the predictability of the results (Yi et al. 2004; Barontini et al. 2013; Forster et al. 2015). The HTP emissions profile reveals a selective reduction of toxicants while maintaining components desired by consumers, ensuring adequate replacement therapy for smokers (Kunze et al. 1998; Abrams et al. 2018a, 2018b; Lee et al. 2020).

The systemic toxicological approach using organotypic human cultures provides biologically relevant evidence of reduced toxicity (Iskandar 2016). Particularly important

are the findings from multiple tissue models, which demonstrate consistent results regardless of tissue type (Zanetti et al. 2016). Epigenetic analyses reveal qualitative differences in the mechanisms of toxicity—HTPs do not induce significant changes in gene expression or histone modifications, unlike cigarette smoke (Iskandar et al. 2017).

The 18-month studies in *A/J* mice represent the gold standard for carcinogenic assessment and provide strong evidence of the reduced carcinogenicity of HTPs compared with CCs (Wong et al. 2020; Xiang et al. 2021). Margin of exposure (MOE) analysis demonstrates that HTPs achieve acceptable safety levels under normal patterns of use (Stephens 2017; Rodrigo et al. 2020; Slob et al. 2020). The 3-year cohort studies in patients with COPD provide clinical evidence of the real health benefits of switching from CCs to HTPs (Polosa et al. 2021). Biomarker data offer objective evidence of reduced exposure in humans (Lüdicke et al. 2016, 2019; Li et al. 2023).

Population data from Japan provide unique real-world evidence of the impact of HTPs at the national level (Cummins et al. 2020). The noticeable decline in cigarette sales, coupled with the growing adoption of HTPs, created a natural experiment to assess population-level effects. Independent studies have revealed the importance of consumption habits in assessing exposure, showing that different patterns of tobacco use affect the levels of exposure to toxicants in humans—with cigarette smoking being the main driver of exposure. This underscores the importance of replacing cigarette smoking with less harmful alternatives to achieve harm reduction (Davigo et al. 2023).

Regulatory applications should include a balanced approach between maximizing benefits for current CC smokers and minimizing the risk of initiation among non-smokers. FDA authorizations for IQOS THS as an MRTP represent an important regulatory validation of the scientific evidence (US FDA 2016, 2020, 2021). Independent confirmations

from European institutions strengthen confidence in these findings (EU 2014; Committee on Toxicity 2017; Auer et al. 2018; Dutch RIVM 2018; Public Health England 2018; Mallock et al. 2019; Superior Health Council Belgium 2020).

Conclusion

The body of scientific evidence demonstrates a consistent and convincing pattern of significantly reduced toxicity in HTPs compared with CCs (Mallock et al. 2019; Slob et al. 2020; US FDA 2021). A multilevel comparative analysis supports the potential for harm reduction when using HTPs as a substitute for cigarette smoking (Abrams et al. 2018a, 2018b; Lee et al. 2020).

Main toxicological highlights:

- **Chemical profile**—HTPs demonstrated an 85–95% reduction in most HPHCs while maintaining nicotine delivery (Inoue-Choi et al. 2016; Schaller et al. 2016a; Jaccard et al. 2017).
- **Biological toxicity**—*In vitro* systems show reduced cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, and inflammatory responses in HTPs (Gonzalez-Suarez et al. 2015; Iskandar et al. 2017).
- **Carcinogenic potential**—18-month *in vivo* studies demonstrated no increase in tumor incidence and significantly lower levels of carcinogenic risk (Wong et al. 2020; Xiang et al. 2021).
- **Clinical benefits**—Prospective cohort studies have shown measurable improvements in lung function and reduced biomarkers of exposure (Lüdicke et al. 2019; Polosa et al. 2021; Li et al. 2023).

HTPs are a scientifically substantiated alternative for smokers who are unable or unwilling to quit tobacco use completely. The harm reduction strategy through HTPs can make a significant contribution to reducing smoking-related morbidity and mortality at the population level.

For health professionals, HTPs may serve as a harm reduction option for smokers who fail to quit using other traditional methods (Committee on Toxicity 2017; Public Health England 2018; Superior Health Council Belgium 2020). For public health, the introduction of HTPs requires balanced policies that maximize benefits for current smokers while minimizing risks for non-smokers. For future research, long-term prospective studies are needed to provide definitive confirmation of benefits (Akram et al. 2024).

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HTPs represent a promising technological advancement in reducing tobacco toxicity as a harm reduction approach. This strategy is based on a solid scientific foundation and demonstrates the potential for significant improvements in public health with appropriate implementation and regulation (Knowledge-Action-Change 2018; Peitsch and Hoeng 2021). Continued research and close monitoring are essential to confirm benefits and minimize risks associated with this innovative technology.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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